

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF TRADE OPENNESS AND FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN SOUTH ASIA: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS

¹Arooj Asif, ^{*2}Atif Khan Jadoon, ³Saima Liaqat, ⁴Sania Zafar

¹School of Economics, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan.

^{*2}School of Economics, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

³Department of Economics, Lahore College for Women University, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴Department of Economics, University of Jhang, Jhang, Pakistan

Email: aamahmood2014@gmail.com

Email: atifkhan.eco@pu.edu.pk

Email: saima.liaqat@lcwu.edu.pk

Email: saniazafar@uoj.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author:

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Atif Khan Jadoon

Abstract

The study analyzes the impact of trade openness and foreign direct investment on economic growth in South Asia. The research uses a balanced panel dataset covering the time period from 2000 to 2023. The main determinants include population growth, gross fixed capital formation, human capital, and institutional quality. The fixed-effects models are estimated using the Hausman test. For a robustness check, the control variables like inflation, globalization, and income inequality are analyzed. Driscoll-Kraay standard errors are used to account for heteroscedasticity and cross-sectional dependence. The baseline results indicate that the major drivers of growth are foreign direct investment, capital formation, human capital, and institutional quality, whereas trade openness and population growth indicate an adverse impact on economic growth. The results suggest that sustainable development depends more on reinforcing the country's core structural fundamentals than on trade liberalization in South Asia. The study recommends that governments may seek to attract productive foreign direct investment, build human capital, and improve institutional quality to sustain long-term economic growth.

1. Introduction

Foreign direct investment (FDI) and trade openness are widely discussed in the literature of development economics and are considered the main drivers of economic growth. The neoclassical and endogenous growth theories indicate that FDI contributes to economic growth in a capital-scarce world by augmenting investment volume and investment efficiency (Barro, 1995; Grossman & Helpman, 1991; Lucas Jr, 1988; Romer, 1986). FDI supports agglomeration economies through industry clustering and network effects, lowering the prices of all commodities in the market (Krugman, 1991; Andreou, 2021; Cizakca, 2024; Soliman, 2025). FDI inflows increase international competition and enhance the host nation's supply-side potential, thereby driving economic growth (Skhirtladze & Nurboja, 2019; Andreou, 2021; Porro & Gia, 2021; Riaz et al., 2024; Saim et al., 2025). Trade openness affects the international flow of capital through the risk-return relationship. As a matter of fact, nobody is interested in making a long-term investment in a country that imposes tariffs and non-tariff barriers on investment and poses issues with the repatriation of capital and profits (Dollar & Kraay, 2004). Trade openness also reflects a nation's comparative advantage in attracting investment (Edward, 1998). According to the transaction cost theory, Williamson (1975) argued

that when the cost of doing business is low, both domestic and foreign investors would gain from long-term investment. Moreover, endogenous growth theories emphasize that an open trade policy framework enhances investment allocative efficiency through specialization (Balasubramanyam et al., 1996). Edwards (1992) also points out that when a country is more economically open, it can expand more rapidly and absorb emerging technologies. The extent of capital formation affects FDI and economic growth (Hwang & Lee, 2019; Sun & Chang, 2020; Mealli, 2021; Weber, 2022). The neo-classical growth model argues that developing economies that initially have a lower capital stock are likely to have higher marginal rates of return and growth rates. The new endogenous growth theories also assume that greater investment efficiency through FDI gives countries with scarce capital a comparative advantage in catching up or converging with richer economies (Romer, 1986). But the beneficial effect of FDI is not predetermined and depends on absorptive capacity, financial development, and institutional quality, in which case FDI can produce insignificant or even negative effects on growth (Carkovic & Levine, 2005; Arshad & Mkhitar, 2019; Naik, 2020; Mordecai & Akinsola, 2021; Khan et al., 2025; Al Rasasi, 2025). Excessive openness may expose developing economies

to external shocks, trade imbalances, and deindustrialization, thereby hindering long-term growth. Furthermore, if domestic investment is crowded out or if FDI is concentrated in low-productivity sectors, the growth benefits may be limited (Alfaro et al., 2004; Alzahrani & Salah, 2020; Irfan & Sohail, 2021; Kumar et al., 2025; Aqeel et al., 2025). FDI and trade openness are expected to drive economic growth, and the relationship may exhibit long-run co-movement. It is, however, unclear whether this positive association holds across all South Asian countries, given their heterogeneity in terms of economic structures, trade patterns, and institutional quality. These dynamics are important to understand to develop region-specific growth policies. The region of South Asia comprises diverse economies in terms of social, organizational, and development levels. These economies include Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Nepal, and Bhutan. The region has seen significant economic change over the last 20 years, largely driven by globalization, trade openness, and FDI (Jadoon et al. 2015; Wang, 2023; Khalid et al., 2025; Alvi & Mudassar, 2025). Trade openness is increasing rapidly due to favorable trade policies. The impact of trade openness and FDI on the economic growth in the South Asian economies is uneven. For example, India and Bangladesh have been fairly effective in promoting

trade openness and FDI to achieve export-oriented industrial growth. Pakistan is facing structural challenges due to political instability, an energy crisis, and weak institutional frameworks (IMF, 2019; Ammar et al., 2025; Soliman, 2025). These differences highlight the need to take into account country-specific and regional-specificities in explaining the trade-FDI-growth nexus.

Further, there are other challenges that limit the benefit from trade and FDI in South Asia. The region's dependence on commodity exports, the high concentration of low-skilled labor, and the lack of export diversification can undermine the positive effects of trade openness (Rossi, 2023; Farhadi & Zhao, 2024; Ditta et al., 2025 Hanvoravongchai & Paweenawat, 2025). Furthermore, FDI inflows can fail to boost growth when they are concentrated in sectors with low domestic interlinkages or subpar institutional quality, thereby impeding the absorption of technology and productivity gains (Hussain & Khan, 2022; Marc et al., 2022; Ibrahim & Simian, 2023). These structural concerns indicate that trade and FDI are not equally growth-promoting across the entire South Asian region and that stringent empirical research is needed that considers macroeconomic, demographic, and institutional variables.

The period from 2000 to 2023 is especially pertinent to studying

these dynamics. The economies faced various global and local shocks, including the global financial crisis of 2008-2009, commodity price volatility, and the COVID-19 pandemic, during this period. These shocks have different impacts on the trade flows, investment choices, and economic outcomes. This study will contribute to the literature by capturing the medium and long-term impacts of trade openness and FDI on economic growth. The study's findings will help address heterogeneity across South Asia's economies. The study has both academic and policy relevance. The study will help fill gaps in the literature on trade openness, FDI, and economic growth in a region that has remained underrepresented. The study will provide insights into trade openness and investment promotion policies to achieve sustainable economic growth. Further, the risks of structural constraints that hinder the effectiveness of these external linkages will be addressed.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical Considerations

The relationship between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Trade Openness (TO), and Economic Growth (EG) is primarily rooted in the evolution of growth theories, moving from neoclassical perspectives to modern endogenous growth models. Unlike neoclassical models (Solow-Swan), which argued that long-run growth arises solely

from exogenous technological progress, Endogenous Growth Theory (Lucas Jr, 1988; Romer, 1986) suggested that policy-related variables, such as trade and FDI, can permanently increase growth rates. FDI is not just a capital inflow; it is a "package" of technology, management practices, and skills. In South Asia, when a multinational corporation sets up operations, local firms often learn through "demonstration effects" or by hiring workers trained by the foreign entity. Trade openness forces domestic firms to compete internationally, incentivizing them to innovate and move up the value chain to survive. This framework suggests that FDI acts as a catalyst for domestic investment. According to Modernization Theory, FDI fills three critical "gaps" in developing regions like South Asia:

1. The Savings-Investment Gap: South Asian countries often have low domestic savings; FDI provides the necessary capital to fund large-scale projects.
2. The Foreign Exchange Gap: FDI helps stabilize the balance of payments.
3. The Technology Gap: FDI introduces advanced machinery and digital processes that are often unavailable in the domestic market.

2.2. Past Empirical studies on the impact of Trade openness, FDI and Economic Growth

Another of the most controversial issues in development economics

has been the association between Trade Openness (TO), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and Economic Growth (EG). Although theoretical models may show a positive nexus, empirical findings remain inconclusive, especially in the South Asian region, where structural rigidities tend to dampen such effects.

2.2.1. Economic Growth and Trade

According to the Prebisch-Singer Hypothesis, primary commodity exporters (as was often the case with South Asian countries) experience a permanent decline in their terms of trade, leading to stagnant growth relative to manufacturers. de Mello, Wittmann, and Friend (1997) research concluded that technology transfer is a significant issue created by FDI. It also brings in different management practices and production methods, which can be emulated by local companies (the "demonstration effect"). According to Newbery and Stiglitz (1984), trade openness exposed one to international price shocks. This volatility in other regions, such as South Asia, may cause macroeconomic instability, hindering long-term investment. Grossman and Helpman (1991) argued that trade stimulates growth, provides access to a greater variety of intermediate inputs, and enables local markets to ride on the shoulders of global innovators through knowledge diffusion. A seminal cross-country study by

Sachs and Warner (1995) found that open economies grew at an average of 4.5 percent per year, while closed economies grew at only 0.7 percent per year. They claimed that trade will enable them to allocate resources more effectively and integrate into the world economy. Alesina, Spolaore, and Wacziarg (2000) argued that small nations benefit from trade openness because it enables them to overcome the constraints of a small domestic market and gain economies of scale. The argument made by in "Kicking Away the Ladder" was that high protectionism was employed by the current developed countries (such as the UK and the USA) to establish their industrial base, and then they promoted free trade, meaning that the current openness in trade would have no chance to allow developing countries to ever become industrialized. In certain developing nations, trade barriers were positively correlated with growth (Yanikkaya, 2003; Marc & Ali, 2023; Marc, 2024; Iqbal et al., 2025). He proposed that the sudden openness may trigger the Dutch Disease or the downfall of local manufacturing, which is still unable to compete with global giants. Dollar and Kraay (2004) singled out a group of so-called post-1980 globalizers (such as India and China) and Wacziarg and Welch (2008) showed that these nations saw a substantial growth and poverty reduction rates directly related to the volumes of their trade.

They revised earlier data and found that liberalized countries experienced 1.5 percentage points of growth relative to the period before liberalization (1950-1998).

2.2.2. Economic Growth and FDI

One of the most famous theories of this kind is Chenery (1967) theory, which posits that foreign capital inflows bridge the so-called savings-investment gap, allowing the country to obtain the funding to construct factories and infrastructure that domestic resources alone cannot finance. Singer (1975) cautioned that FDI usually forms islands of wealth. As an example, one can take a foreign mine that is very high-tech and profitable, but does not purchase any products from local suppliers, does not employ local managers, and the rest of the country sees no gains (Ali & Naeem, 2017; Marc & Ali, 2018; Ahmad et al., 2022; Hamza et al., 2025).

The contribution to permanent growth, as proposed by Romer (1990) and Lucas Jr (1988), is that the knowledge acquired through FDI does not vanish; it remains with locals even after the foreign firm leaves. Dutt and Sen (1997) suggested that global corporations tend to exploit their wealth to establish monopolies in third-world countries, thereby slowing technological development and increasing prices for local residents. A study by Borensztein et al. (1998) found that a threshold level of human capital (education) is

required by the host country to achieve FDI-driven growth. The spillovers do not occur without competent manpower to operate the new technology. According to Lall (2000), FDI assists developing countries in moving from trading in primary raw materials (such as crops) to trading in advanced manufactured products, by creating connections between them and global supply chains.

Agosin and Mayer (2000) found that, in most cases, FDI does not contribute to the economy; it merely substitutes for local investment. When a massive multinational company enters, small local businesses may fail to survive because they cannot compete, and no net growth will be realized. According to Alfaro et al. (2004), FDI only has its magic to play in nations with strong banks and stock exchanges. Failure by the local entrepreneurs to obtain loans to establish businesses halts growth. Carkovic and Levine (2005) analyzed a large dataset and concluded that there is no magic in FDI after controlling for other variables. They say that FDI concentrates on growth that is already occurring rather than being the cause of such growth. Hansen and Rand (2006) examined the statistics of 31 developing nations and found a causal relationship between FDI and increased GDP, as local industry becomes more productive due to competition. Busse and Hefeker

(2007) argued that it is more important to make FDI productive in countries with stronger institutions, such as fair legal systems, low corruption, and political stability. Findlay (1978) proposed that the gap between the foreign tech and local tech should be just right. When the foreign company is too sophisticated, local companies cannot learn how to do it; if it is too close, there is nothing new to learn.

2.2.3. Economic Growth and Capital

According to Mankiw et al. (1992) and Young (1995), the main reason for the Asian miracle was the massive mobilization of physical capital. Some of the main forms of capital during this period were heavy machinery and factory floor equipment. In South Asia, Sahoo (2012) concluded that a precondition for private investment was the presence of public infrastructure (roads and energy). Easterly and Rebelo (1993) argued that some forms of investment in public capital were strongly associated with long-term growth. According to recent works such as Mahmood et al. (2024) Digital Capital (broadband, AI servers, and high-tech grids) contributed indirectly to economic growth through productivity gains and improved resource allocation. Moreover, according to Khan and Siddiqui (2025), Green Investment, as an investment in renewable energy infrastructure, is a new requirement for sustainable GDP

growth in the context of climate vulnerability.

2.2.4. Economic Growth and Population

Lucas Jr (1988) and R. J. Barro (1991) shifted the focus from the number of workers to the quality of the workforce. Psacharopoulos (1994) confirmed that the payback to education was greatest in the developing world, particularly in South Asia. The authors D. Bloom, Canning, and Sevilla (2003) discovered the so-called Demographic Dividend as one of the opportunities of South Asia. But according to Besley and Burgess (2004), this "dividend" was not taking its true form due to India's strict labor laws. Hanushek and Woessmann (2020) argue that years of schooling are an outdated measure and that cognitive skills and learning outcomes are the two factors driving growth today. The authors emphasize the rise of the so-called Gig Economy and remote digital labor as one of the most significant structural changes in South Asian labor markets, which demand new forms of institutional protection.

2.2.5. Economic Growth and Institutions

North (1990) and Acemoglu, Johnson, and Robinson (2001) have transformed the growth theory by claiming that institutions (property rights and rule of law) are the main reason of development. Evans and Rauch (1999) demonstrated that

economies with merit-based bureaucracies can take off. Mehlum, Moene, and Torvik (2006) investigated the role of extractive institutions in South Asia that fostered cronyism. The Sri Lankan economic crisis of 2022 served as a contemporary example of how institutional failures (poor debt management and the absence of central bank independence) can lead to an economic collapse (Perera et al., 2023; Ali et al., 2025). Recent studies by Ullah et al. (2024) focus on the concept of Institutional Resilience, the capacity of a nation's legal and political system to withstand shocks in the global arena.

In South Asia, population "explosions" were a major concern because they slowed per-capita growth. D. E. Bloom and Williamson (1998) shifted the story to the Demographic Dividend, demonstrating that the young workforce in South Asia could boost regional growth if combined with employment. Headey and Hodge (2009) affirmed that population growth is detrimental to the poorest but supports transitions between middle-income brackets. The risks posed by the Youth Bulge and the colossal contribution of out-migration and remittances to regional development have become the subject of current research (Cincotta, 2008; Rajan, 2023). The discussion in 2025 is whether South Asia will age before becoming rich (World Bank, 2024; Ali et al., 2025).

2.2.6. Economic Growth and Control Variables

2.2.6.1. Economic growth and Inflation

Fischer (1993) and R. J. Barro (2013) determined that high inflation built a fog of price uncertainty that killed long-term incentives to invest.

A study conducted by (Khan, Senhadji, and Smith (2006) specified that a critical value (between 7 and 11 percent in the case of developing countries) beyond which inflation is highly harmful to GDP growth. A similar threshold of 9% was affirmed by Mubarak (2005) for the South Asian environment.

2.2.6.2. Economic growth and Globalization

In an attempt to demonstrate how powerful economic flows are, Dreher (2006) used the KOF Index to demonstrate that Social Globalization (ideas and people) is equally powerful. Stiglitz (2002) warned about the dangers of unregulated financial globalization. Gurgul and Lach (2014) noted the spread of democratic and market-oriented norms through globalization. Savrul and Incekara (2015) examined how the global supply chain integration affects the small-scale South Asian companies. The tech rivalry between global giants and digital connectivity is a new factor in advancing the South Asian region. Recent research by Lang and Tavares (2024) globalization gains are unevenly distributed and increase inequality

within country and regional disparities.

2.2.6.3. Economic growth and income inequality

Persson and Tabellini (1994) put forth that inequality is a source of social unrest and redistributive demands that are detrimental to investment. Alesina and Rodrik (1994) found that high land tenure inequality was associated with low growth. The results from Forbes (2000) were somewhat contradictory, and inequality may stimulate saving in some settings and inhibit human capital investment in others. Berg and Ostry (2011) demonstrated that the longer a society sustains sustainable growth, the more equal it is. The Imported Inflation and Energy Inflation are discussed in post-pandemic research (Perveez, 2019; Perera et al., 2023; shahabuddin & Ali, 2024; Ali et al., 2025; Liu & Cai, 2025). In 2025, the literature states that the most important institutional moderator of growth derailment in volatile economies is Central Bank Independence.

Although a number of studies have been conducted on the correlation between trade openness and economic growth, much of the existing literature, like the one provided by Seti, Mazwane, and Christian (2025), covers a general group of emerging and developing economies, and in many cases, the study takes an approach that encompasses financial openness in

addition to openness to trade. Nonetheless, regional studies in South Asia are rather sparse, especially those that simultaneously examine trade openness and foreign direct investment (FDI) as independent drivers of economic growth (Siddiqi et al., 2014; Ahmed et al., 2018; Zahid, 2018; Bashir & Rashid, 2019; Audi et al., 2021; Ali & Audi, 2023; Ahmed & Rura, 2024; Karul & Nawaz, 2025). In particular, given the importance of openness to growth, South Asian economies exhibit distinct features, such as differences in institutional quality, trade policies, and reliance on FDI inflows, which may not yield the same effects in other regions. The paper provides a fine-grained, context-sensitive examination of the effects of trade liberalization and FDI inflows on South Asian countries, pinpointing areas that can inform policymakers in the region.

3. Data, Model and Methodology

3.1. Data Description

This research employs a balance panel data of 6 South Asian¹ economies (Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Nepal and Bhutan) covering the time span of 2000-2023 to examine the association between Economic Growth (EG), Trade openness (TO) and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) while considering Pop (POP), Capital

¹ Maldives and Afghanistan are not included in this research because of non-availability of data of some variables.

gains observed when comparing the results of common least-squares regressions (OLS) on individual cross-sections. To select the type of unit root test, the CD test is applied. This paper utilizes the CD test (M. H. Pesaran, 2021).

3.5. Panel Unit Root Test

To verify data stationarity, unit root tests are performed. To obtain credible findings, the unit root test must be conducted if panel data values are identified as non-stationary. For cross-sectional independent variables, the first-generation unit root test (M. Pesaran, Shin, & Smith, 1997) is used; for cross-sectional dependent variables, the cross-sectional augmented Im, Pesaran, and Shin (CIPS) unit root test is applied.

3.6. Fixed Effect Model (FEM)

The fixed effects model assumes that the effects of time-invariant, immeasurable factors can be represented by time-invariant, individual-specific dummy variables. It allows one to examine the time dependence of within-unit changes. The fixed-effect estimator is also known as the least-squares dummy variable (LSDV) estimator. Dummy variables would allow us to estimate each segment's constant using group-specific values.

3.7. Random Effect Model (REM)

Along with the FE model, another method for estimating panel data is the random effects technique (Arshad, Jadoon, Sarwar, & Javaid,

2024). In contrast to the FEM, the constant term is treated as a random variable with a known mean in the RE model. The equation above suggests that an intercept term, which captures the unique features of each entity, must include a random error component, commonly known as the individual error component. The value of AI would vary due to the random error component as per the equation. The explanatory factors are believed to have no relationship to a specific error component.

3.8. Hausman Test

The Hausman test is used to decide between the FEM and REM. The null hypothesis of the Hausman test is that there is no relationship between the error component and the exogenous variable. If the null hypothesis is rejected, the REM will be used to obtain unbiased estimators. We shall estimate using fixed effects.

3.9. Post Estimation Test

To achieve unbiased and BLUE9 results, the estimates should not be affected by heteroscedasticity. This study employed the Breusch-Pagan test to remove heteroskedasticity. This test can be applied to both balanced and imbalanced panels. The hypotheses are:

Ho: The residual values are homoscedastic.

H1: The residual values are heteroskedastic.

4. Estimation results and Discussions

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 2

Summary Statistics of Variables

Variables	Mean	St.Dev	Min	Max	Obs
GDP _{it}	7.29221	.5581471	6.304853	8.410284	144
TO _{it}	49.4012	21.32676	21.45996	108.1578	
FDI _{it}	.9477447	.8519549	-.6388063	5.881323	
POP _{it}	1.210054	.7083733	-2.799683	2.82476	
GFCF _{it}	32.42047	13.0747	13.96815	69.44873	
HC _{it}	62.52299	24.66119	21.85283	100.878	
INS _{it}	-.9892199	.8414122	-2.482955	.5733886	
INF _{it}	7.281726	5.419301	2.007174	49.7211	
GLOB _{it}	47.74306	9.151213	25	60	
GINI _{it}	5.344359	3.958933	-9.738144	25.07203	

Authors calculations

The sample of 144 observations is presented in Table 2, along with descriptive statistics. The average value of GDP per capita (log) is 7.29, with a standard deviation of 6.30 to 8.41 across South Asian countries. The extent of trade openness is great (mean 49.4% of GDP), with a wide range of 21.5% to 108.2%, and FDI inflows are also low at 0.95% of GDP, ranging from -0.64 to 5.88, indicating variation in investment attractiveness. The average population growth is 1.21%, with a range of -2.80 to 2.82, indicating population variability. The

difference in human capital, proxied by education, is quite notable, with a mean of 62.5 and a range of 21.85 to 100.88. Institutional quality is poor, with an average of -0.99, and inflation is not high but volatile, with an average of 7.28 and a high of 49.72. Globalization is moderately varied with an average of 47.7 and a range of 25 to 60. Lastly, income inequality is highly heterogeneous across nations, providing sufficient variation to determine the impact of economic growth and openness to trade and FDI.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Table 3

Correlation Outcomes

Indicators	EG _{it}	TO _{it}	FDI _{it}	POP _{it}	GFCF _{it}	HC _{it}	INS _{it}
EG _{it}	1.0000						
TO _{it}	0.4239	1.0000					
FDI _{it}	0.1963	0.1838	1.0000				
POP _{it}	-0.3333	-0.1805	0.0619	1.0000			
GFCF _{it}	0.3686	0.7484	0.0741	-0.1841	1.0000		

HCit	0.6912	0.4210	0.0537	-0.6729	0.4069	1.0000	
INSit	0.6253	0.6054	0.2461	-0.0812	0.5548	0.4704	1.0000

The correlation matrix of the table 3 indicates that the economy growth has a positive relationship with human capital (0.69), institutional quality (0.63), trade openness (0.42), and gross fixed capital formation (0.37) and a negative relationship with population growth (-0.33) which implies that these factors that increase economic growth are higher education, high governance, openness, and investment capital. The openness to trade is closely related to investment (0.75) and institutions (0.61), suggesting that more open economies are likely to be more attractive to investment and to have superior levels of

governance. FDI shows a positive, though weak, correlation with growth (0.20), trade openness (0.18), and institutions (0.25), suggesting that it may have conditional effects on growth. Human capital (negatively correlated at -0.67) and investment (negatively correlated at -0.18) negatively affect population growth, suggesting that rapid population growth may have limits. On the whole, the matrix shows moderate to high correlations among the important variables, providing sufficient separation to study their impact on economic growth without serious multicollinearity problems.

4.3. Cross Section Dependence and Panel Unit Root Test

Table 4

CD and Panel Unit Root results

Variables	CD P-value	CD Status	IPS At level	1 st diff	Order	(CIPS) At level	1 st diff	Order
TO _{it}	0.000*	Dep				-2.447**	-----	I(0)
FDI _{it}	0.001*	Dep				-3.538*	-----	I(0)
POP _{it}	0.000*	Dep				-1.605	-2.339**	I(1)
GFCF _{it}	0.405	Ind	0.2611	0.000*	I(1)	-0.678	-3.251*	I(1)
HC _{it}	0.000*	Dep				-1.558	-4.533*	I(1)
INS _{it}	0.280	Ind	0.0920***	-----	I(0)			
INF _{it}	0.000*	Dep				-3.025*	----	I(0)
GLOB _{it}	0.000*	Dep				-2.370***	----	I(0)
GINI _{it}	0.000*					-3.227*	-----	I(0)

Authors Calculation

Notes: IPS use p-value while CIPS use calculated values and critical values. Critical values in case of

CIPS are -2.21 -2.33 -2.57 at 10%, 5% and 1% level of significance. *, **and *** denotes level of

significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

4.4. Fixed Effects and Random Effects Estimation Results

The Fixed Effects (FE) model was first estimated, and then the Random Effects (RE) model. The Hausman test is carried out to identify the best specification. The Hausman test results indicated a p - value of 0.000, which is statistically significant at the 5% level. Thus, it was accepted that the null

hypothesis of the Random Effects model was inappropriate, and the Fixed Effects model was chosen as the preferred estimation method. When we ran a diagnostic test, it revealed heteroskedasticity. To address this issue, we have computed the Driscoll-Kraay standard errors (D-KSE). The second section has a detailed presentation of the amended results. Results are reported in the subsequent Table 5.

Table 5

Fixed Effects Results

Dependent Variable: Economic Growth(EGit)				
Variables	Coeff	S.E	t-value	P-value
TOit	-.005462	.001523	-3.59	0.000*
FDI _{it}	.0398133	.0192973	2.06	0.041**
POP _{it}	-.1154139	.0275071	-4.20	0.000 *
GFCF _{it}	.0092533	.0025094	3.69	0.000*
HC _{it}	.0135679	.0009917	13.68	0.000*
INS _{it}	.1579639	.0462747	3.41	0.000*
CONS	6.671922	.1347265	49.52	0.000*
Summary Statistics				
Obs.				144
Prob> F(FE)				0.0000*
R2				0.7594
Hausman Test Outcome:				
Prob> chi2				0.000*
Diagnostic Tests Outcomes:				
BP Heteroskedasticity Test [H0: constant variance]				
Prob> chi2				0.0000*
Conclusion				Heteroskedasticity

Source: Authors calculations

Notes: *, **and *** denotes level of significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

4.5. Panel FEM Results (D-KSE): 2000-2023

Driscoll and Kraay standard errors are reported in Table 6 to address possible heteroskedasticity and cross-sectional dependence in the panel data. There are also additional control variables, inflation, globalization, and income inequality,

Table 6

which we use to verify the strength of our baseline estimates. The additions enable us to test whether the relations between trade openness, FDI, population growth, capital formation, human capital, and institutions with economic growth are stable across alternative model specifications.

Panel FEM Results with GLS and D-KSE

Dependent Variable: Economic Growth(EGit)				
Regression Number				
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
Variables	Coeff/ p-value/S.E	Coeff/ p-value/S.E	Coeff/ p-value/S.E	Coeff/ p-value/S.E
TOit	-.0055 (0.000*) [.0015]	-.0058 (0.000*) [.0015]	-.0063 (0.000*) [.0015]	-.00614 (0.000*) [.0015]
FDI _{it}	.0398 (0.041**) [.0193]	.0381 (0.000*) [.0192]	.0332 (0.087***) [.0192]	.0359 (0.067***) [.0194]
POP _{it}	-.1154 (0.000*) [.0275]	-.1096 (0.000*) [.0276]	-.0936 (0.001*) [.0287]	-.0987 (0.001*) [.0292]
GFCF _{it}	.0092 (0.000*) [.0025]	.0095 (0.000*) [.0025]	.00959 (0.000*) [.0024]	.01021 (0.000*) [.0026]
HC _{it}	.0136 (0.000*) [.0010]	.0135 (0.000*) [.0010]	.01035 (0.000*) [.0019]	.01030 (0.000*) [.00196]
INS _{it}	.1579 (0.001*) [.0462]	.1731 (0.000*) [.0471]	.1791 (0.000*) [.0467]	.1788 (0.000*) [.0467]
INFit		.0040 (0.125) [.0025]	.0036 (0.166) [.0026]	.00261 (0.346) [.0028]
GLOBit			.5747 (0.061***) [.3047]	.54208 (0.080***) [.3067]

GINIit				-.00354 (0.344) [.0037]
R2	0.7594	0.7637	0.7700	0.7716

Source: Author's own-calculation
Note: *, ** and *** denotes significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

The Fixed Effects regression (1.1) is used to investigate the determinants of economic growth (EG) in South Asian nations. A 1% increase in trade openness decreases per capita GDP growth by 0.55% when other factors remain unchanged. This negative correlation is congruent with the literature by Yanikkaya (2003), who concluded that in certain developing nations, abrupt trade liberalization may damage the domestic industries that are not yet competitive, slowing growth in the short term. Structural constraints can lead to an initially negative effect of trade openness in South Asia.

An influx of FDI by 1 % will improve the growth of the economy by an average of 3.98% ceteris paribus. This result is supported by Balasubramanyam et al. (1996) and Asiedu (2002), who argue that FDI is a driver of growth through capital and technology inflows as well as managerial skills. The positive effect shows that the economies of South Asia benefit from foreign investment, albeit to a moderate extent.

A 1% increase in population decreases per capita GDP growth by an average of 11%. The high population growth rates erode

capital and human resources per capita, in line with the neoclassical growth model of Solow (1956), which forecasts that high population growth rates may lower per capita output in economies with very low levels of capital.

A 1% increase in GFCF elevates growth by 0.92%. This positive impact is consistent with the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories of Romer (1986) and Lucas Jr (1988), which argue that capital accumulation increases productive capacity and long-term growth.

A 1% rise in human capital boosts the growth by 1.36%. It aligns with R. J. Barro (1991), who argues that higher education and skills increase labor productivity and contribute to economic growth.

One unit of institutional quality improvement increases per capita growth by approximately 15.8%. Well-established institutions promote investment and will facilitate effective allocation of resources (Acemoglu et al., 2001). The beneficial impact supports the claim that governance, the rule of law, and political stability are key to South Asian development.

In the 1.2 specification, including inflation in the regression does not have a statistically significant impact on economic growth in South Asia over the sample period. Stable

growth could not be limited by moderate inflation in the region, or the inflationary effect on growth is nullified by other factors such as FDI, human capital, and institutions. This is in line with study of R. J. Barro (2013), which indicates that high and volatile inflation is the only growth-damaging phenomenon. Including inflation does not alter the direction or meaning of the baseline determinants (TO, FDI, POP, GFCF, HC, INS). This implies that the main growth drivers are strong, and the inflation does not confound their impact. The degree of inflation does not matter, so moderate inflation variation in South Asia has little influence on per capita GDP growth in the presence of other structural variables.

In specification 1.3, we include globalization in the regression. The positive, but small, effect on growth is the increase driven by globalization. It is an important part of FDI, trade, and capital formation, but it is not as powerful as structural factors such as institutions and human capital. Trade openness still has a negative impact on growth, possibly because globalization tends to distribute benefits unevenly through the integration process. Remaining positive and significant, albeit slightly lower, are FDI, GFCF, human capital, and institutions. The problem of population growth keeps per capita output from declining. An increase in R^2 indicates that globalization provides additional

explanatory power, thereby reducing the unexplained variation in growth not accounted for by traditional factors.

We also include income inequality as a control variable in specification 1.4. Income inequality has little impact on growth in South Asia, suggesting that structural factors (FDI, human capital, institutions, and capital formation) have a greater impact. Trade openness is negative. FDI, GFCF, human capital, and institutions are positive and significant. Economic growth is still being hampered by population growth. Internationalization remains favorable, and inflation is negligible. The increase in R^2 is also low, suggesting that GINI fails to explain growth as well as other variables when introduced. Inequality can have little effect on growth in new and developing economies when capital, human capital, and institutions are taken into account (R. J. Barro, 2000).

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This study provides an empirical analysis of the impact of trade openness and FDI on economic growth in South Asia. It explicitly accounts for structural heterogeneity, institutional quality, and human capital accumulation. The analysis reveals that FDI, human capital, gross fixed capital formation, and institutional quality are robust, statistically significant drivers of economic growth, highlighting the

critical interplay between external capital inflows and domestic absorptive capacity. Conversely, the negative association between trade openness and growth underscores the nuanced, context-dependent nature of liberalization in developing regions. It suggests that premature or unaccompanied trade liberalization may exacerbate structural vulnerabilities, particularly in economies with low competitiveness or high population growth.

The robustness checks, including the incorporation of inflation, globalization, and income inequality, confirm that the baseline estimates are consistent. Inflation exhibits no significant effect, globalization exerts a modest positive influence, and income inequality does not materially alter growth dynamics once key structural factors are controlled for. These findings align with endogenous growth frameworks, emphasizing that long-run growth is driven less by short-term macroeconomic shocks and more by productive investments, human capital accumulation, and institutional efficiency.

From a policy perspective, the results imply that South Asian economies must adopt a strategically sequenced approach to FDI and trade liberalization, complementing external openness with domestic capacity-building. Policies should prioritize promoting high-quality FDI, investing in education and skill

development, and implementing institutional reforms to create an enabling environment for sustainable growth. Moreover, the study underscores that cross-country heterogeneity within South Asia necessitates nuanced, country-specific policy prescriptions, rather than blanket regional strategies.

Overall, this research advances the literature by providing a context-sensitive, empirically grounded analysis of the trade-FDI-growth nexus, demonstrating that the efficacy of external linkages in promoting growth is conditional upon strong domestic fundamentals and institutional quality. These insights have both academic and policy relevance, offering a refined understanding of the mechanisms through which openness and investment can translate into sustained economic development in emerging regions.

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